

Stobbe Condensation with Ethyl Methyl Ketone

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ETHYL methyl ketone on Stobbe condensation with arylidenesuccinate (**1a**, Ar=Ph, *p*-(oMe) C₆H₄) at room temperature for 1 h gave the oily acid-esters that on saponification yielded the crystallisable diacids (**2g** and **2h**, Ar=Ph, *p*-(oMe) C₆H₄)^{1,2}. In an alternative method 1,2-dicarbomethoxy-3-methylpent-2-ene (**1c, d**) on Stobbe condensation with aryl aldehydes (Ar=Ph, *p*-(oMe) C₆H₄) at room temperature yielded of mixture of isomers of acid-esters (**2c** and **2d**, Ar=Ph, *p*-(oMe) C₆H₄) that on saponification gave the corresponding diacids (**2g** and **2h**, Ar=Ph, *p*-(oMe) C₆H₄).

In the present study, Stobbe condensation^{3,4} of benzhydrylidenesuccinate (**1b**) and ethyl methyl

ketone in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide at room temperature for 1 h and usual work-up yielded the acid-esters (**2e** and **2f**, Ar=Ph) which were separated by crystallisation as acid-ester *cis*-isomer (**2e**, Ar=Ph), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 75.51; H, 6.27; equiv. wt. 350.41. C₂₂H₃₂O₄ requires: C, 75.41; H, 6.33%; equiv. wt. 350.39); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 720, 1 675 and 1 218 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.69–1.00 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 1.69 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.63–2.31 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 7.22 (10H, s, ArH); acid-ester *trans*-isomer (**2f**, Ar=Ph), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 75.36; H, 6.29; equiv. wt. 351.1. C₂₂H₃₂O₄ requires: C, 75.41; H, 6.33%; equiv. wt. 350.39); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 718, 1 680 and 1 218 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.70–0.95 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 1.95 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.92 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂), 3.45 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 7.21 (10H, s, ArH).

The *cis*-acid-ester (**2e**, Ar=Ph) on saponification with 8% alcoholic KOH gave exclusively the *cis*-diacid (**2i**, Ar=Ph), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 75.01; H, 5.88; equiv. wt. 167.82. C₂₁H₂₀O₄ requires: C, 74.98; H, 5.99%; equiv. wt. 168.19); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 280.5 and 320.8 nm (log ϵ 4.47 and 3.94); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 693, 1 610 and 1 225 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.62–0.80 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 1.66 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.00 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂) and 6.85–7.60 (10H, m, ArH). The *trans*-acid-ester (**2f**, Ar=Ph) on saponification similarly gave exclusively the *trans*-diacid (**2j**, Ar=Ph), m.p. 196° (Found: C, 75.14; H, 5.91; equiv. wt. 169.16. C₂₁H₂₀O₄ requires: C, 74.98; H, 5.99%; equiv. wt. 168.19); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 280.8 and 318.2 nm (log ϵ 4.48 and 3.88); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 683, 1 590 and 1 208 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.70–0.88 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 2.14 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.00 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂) and 6.65–7.50 (10H, m, ArH).

In an alternative method, the crude acid-esters (**2e, f**, Ar=Ph) were directly saponified to give the geometrical isomeric mixture of the diacids (**2i** and **2j**, Ar=Ph). On crystallisation with benzene-*n*-hexane, the crude diacid deposited two types of crystals. The first type comprising of big crystals which after handpicking and crystallisation gave the pure *trans*-diacid (**2j**, Ar=Ph) that was identical to **2j** reported earlier, and second type of isomer of the diacid was crystallised to yield the *cis*-diacid (**2i**, Ar=Ph) that was identical to the **2i** made earlier. The *cis*- and *trans*-isomers were characterised on the basis of chemical shift values in the pmr spectra of the diacids (**2e–f**) for the OCH₃, CH₃ and C₂H₅ protons by comparison with previous molecules (**2a, b** and **2c, d**)¹.

The *cis*-diacid (**2i**, Ar=Ph; 1.0 g) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (10 ml) for 2 h and then excess acetyl chloride was removed to yield the *cis*-acid-anhydride (**3a**; crystallised by benzene-*n*-hexane), m.p. 121° (Found: C, 79.71; H, 5.81. C₂₁H₁₈O₃ requires: C, 79.26; H, 5.64%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 281, 318.2 and 252.3 nm (log ϵ 5.01, 4.18 and 5.09); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 810, 1 765 and 1 215 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.91–1.15 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 1.24 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.53–2.90 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂) and 7.24 (10H, s, ArH). **3a** (1.0 g).

3a (1.0 g) was treated with anhydrous AlCl_3 and nitrobenzene at 0° for 24 h, the mixture then acidified with 6*N* HCl and nitrobenzene distilled off. It was then extracted in ether, then in ice-cold 10% Na_2CO_3 solution and acidified with concentrated HCl to yield a solid which was crystallised from benzene-*n*-hexane as a deep chrome yellow indenone⁶ (**4a**), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 79.50; H, 5.41; equiv. wt. 318.51. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 79.22; H, 5.69%; equiv. wt. 318.35); λ_{max} (EtOH) 280.8, 318.2 and 395.2 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.77, 4.41 and 3.98); ν_{max} 1 712, 1 695, 1 622, 1 610, 1 587 and 1 275 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.88–1.12 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.51 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.40–2.74 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH_2) and 7.08–7.55 (9H, m, ArH). The same indenone (**4a**) was also obtained from the *cis*-diacid (**2i**, Ar=Ph) when it was treated with concentrated H_2SO_4 at 0° .

Similarly, the *trans*-diacid (**2j**, Ar=Ph) yielded the *trans*-acid-anhydride (**3b**), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 79.14; H, 5.81. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 79.26; H, 5.64%; λ_{max} (EtOH) 279.8, 318.2 and 350.0 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.41, 4.20 and 4.25); ν_{max} 1 809, 1 760 and 1 217 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.76–0.98 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.38–1.70 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH_2) and 7.13 (10H, s, ArH), which on internal Friedel-Crafts cyclisation with anhydrous AlCl_3 yielded the corresponding indenone (**4b**), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 79.50; H, 5.63; equiv. wt. 318.10. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 79.22; H, 5.69%; equiv. wt. 318.35); λ_{max} (EtOH) 277.8, 318.2 and 394.5 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 5.49, 5.04 and 4.34); ν_{max} 1 710, 1 690, 1 625, 1 612, 1 590 and 1 255 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.57–0.75 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.11 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.75–2.25 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH_2) and 7.03–7.55 (9H, m, ArH). The same indenone (**4b**) was obtained when the *trans*-diacid (**2j**, Ar=Ph) was treated with concentrated H_2SO_4 at 0° .

The separated diacids (**2i** and **2j**, Ar=Ph) did not undergo cyclisation with PPA at 100° .

Pmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, ir spectra recorded in KBr/nujol and uv spectra (EtOH) on a Varian DMS-80 spectrophotometer.

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- 1a**; $\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Ar}$
b; $\text{R}^1=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Ph}$
c; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$
d; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$

2

- 2a**; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
b; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
c; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{Me}$
d; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{Me}$
e; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
f; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
g; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
h; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
i; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$
j; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^3=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}^4=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$

3

- 3a**; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$
b; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$

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- 4a**; $\text{R}^1=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Et}$
b; $\text{R}^1=\text{Et}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Me}$

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